

Bid-Rigging Detection under Label Scarcity: Learning Curves and Jurisdiction-Specific Screening

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Abstract

Machine learning methods are increasingly used to screen for bid rigging in public procurement. Prior research shows that supervised models can substantially improve on traditional screening rules when a sufficiently rich archive of confirmed cartel cases is available, but it also suggests that predictive performance may deteriorate when models are transferred across jurisdictions with different procurement environments. In practice, these constraints may arise jointly: confirmed domestic cartel cases may be scarce, and models trained elsewhere may not transport reliably to a different institutional setting.

This work studies that joint problem directly. Using a multi-jurisdiction dataset of 40,960 bids from confirmed cartel and competitive tenders, we first evaluate cross-jurisdiction transfer by training models on all jurisdictions except the target one and testing them on the excluded jurisdiction. We then estimate within-country learning curves under extreme label scarcity by varying the absolute number of labeled tenders available for training. The results point to a consistent pattern. Cross-jurisdiction transfer often deteriorates materially, reinforcing earlier evidence that collusive bidding patterns are not fully portable across procurement environments. In our benchmark, these losses appear especially marked once performance is evaluated relative to a local oracle on a prevalence-adjusted scale. At the same time, supervised gradient boosting recovers a substantial share of attainable local performance with relatively small labeled sets in some jurisdictions, although the rate of recovery is highly heterogeneous. In this benchmark, the interaction between label scarcity and institutional heterogeneity appears more constraining than label scarcity on its own. These findings suggest that, in settings like ours, even a modest domestic labeled archive can be valuable when authorities seek to build jurisdiction-specific screening tools.

Keywords: Bid rigging | Cartel screening | Public procurement | Machine learning
| Label scarcity | Cross-jurisdiction generalization | Learning curves

1 Introduction

Bid rigging in public procurement undermines competition and can generate substantial welfare losses. Detecting such practices is therefore a central task for competition authorities,

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yet it remains empirically challenging. A long-standing literature develops statistical and econometric screens based on bidding patterns such as dispersion, relative positioning, or uniformity to flag suspicious tenders (Imhof et al., 2018; Imhof, 2019). More recent work shows that supervised machine learning can substantially improve predictive accuracy when a sufficiently rich archive of confirmed cartel cases is available (Huber and Imhof, 2019; Imhof and Wallimann, 2021; Huber and Imhof, 2023).

In practice, however, the evidentiary base required to construct such labeled datasets may be costly to assemble. Confirmed cartel cases typically emerge from court rulings, leniency applications, or extensive investigations, and in some institutional settings the available domestic archive may remain limited. A further complication is that collusive bidding patterns need not be stable across procurement environments. Prior research documents deteriorating predictive performance when screening models are transferred across jurisdictions, reflecting differences in procurement rules, auction formats, market organization, bidder composition, and the structure of cartelized tenders (Imhof and Wallimann, 2021; Huber et al., 2022; Huber and Imhof, 2023). This limits the portability of screening systems and implies that authorities should not assume, without validation, that a model trained in one country will be equally informative in another.

Taken together, these constraints raise a practical question for enforcement. If models trained abroad do not generalize reliably to a target jurisdiction, can authorities with only a modest domestic labeled archive still build useful jurisdiction-specific screening tools? More concretely, how many domestic tenders must be labeled before a local supervised model recovers a substantial share of the best attainable within-jurisdiction performance?

This paper addresses that question through a two-part empirical design. First, we evaluate cross-jurisdiction transfer by training models on all jurisdictions except the target one and testing them on the excluded jurisdiction—that is, through leave-one-domain-out (LODO) evaluation. This exercise provides direct evidence on the limits of model portability across institutional settings. Second, we estimate within-country learning curves under extreme label scarcity by varying the absolute number of labeled tenders available for training. This design translates predictive performance into a policy-relevant object: the amount of domestic labeled evidence that may be required to recover strong local screening performance when external transfer is imperfect.

This study makes two contributions. First, it re-examines the imperfect transportability of bid-rigging models across jurisdictions under a prevalence-adjusted comparison against a local oracle. The transfer results reinforce the view that procurement rules, market organization, and bidding behaviour generate consequential domain-specific variation, so that cross-jurisdiction deployment should be approached cautiously (Huber et al., 2022; Huber and Imhof, 2023). Second, it offers, to our knowledge, the first systematic characterization of within-country learning curves under extreme label scarcity in bid-rigging detection. We show that local learning under extreme label scarcity is highly heterogeneous across jurisdictions: in some cases, relatively small labeled domestic seeds recover a substantial share of the attainable local supervised benchmark, while in others recovery remains much slower over the main experimental grid.

These findings have direct implications for the design of data-driven enforcement strategies. The results suggest that the key constraint in this benchmark is not label scarcity in isolation, but its interaction with limited transportability across jurisdictions. When institutional

heterogeneity is substantial, even a modest stock of local labeled tenders can be more informative than foreign training data used without adaptation. The contribution of this work is therefore not to estimate collusion prevalence in procurement markets, but to characterize the practical feasibility of jurisdiction-specific screening under a curated benchmark built from confirmed cartel and competitive tenders.

The remainder of the paper is structured as follows. Section 2 reviews the relevant existing literature. Section 3 presents the construction and description of the dataset. The experimental design is described in Section 4, before presenting the results in Section 5. Finally, we conclude in Section 6.

2 Related Literature

This work relates to three strands of literature.

First, a long-standing industrial-organization literature studies statistical and econometric screens for detecting bid rigging in procurement auctions. These approaches use summary patterns of bidding behaviour—such as dispersion, relative positioning, or uniformity—to flag suspicious tenders. Imhof et al. (2018) evaluate combinations of screens in Swiss road construction, while Imhof (2019) shows that descriptive bidding patterns can distinguish collusive from competitive tenders under specific cartel settings. These methods are transparent and interpretable, but their performance may depend on the institutional environment in which they are applied.

Second, a more recent literature integrates machine learning with screen-based variables in order to improve predictive accuracy in supervised cartel detection. Huber and Imhof (2019) show that supervised machine-learning methods using screen variables achieve strong predictive performance in detection tasks. Subsequent work extends this approach to alternative representations of bidding interactions and coalition structures, including cross-country and auction-format settings (Imhof and Wallimann, 2021; Huber and Imhof, 2023). Related contributions also include large-sample machine-learning evaluations of procurement-risk indicators (Fazekas et al., 2026) and newer network-based representations of procurement markets (Imhof et al., 2025). Across this literature, the central lesson is that supervised learning can improve substantially on standalone screens when labeled cartel examples are available.

Third, several papers suggest that such gains may not transfer cleanly across institutional settings. In particular, Imhof and Wallimann (2021) and Huber et al. (2022) show that performance may deteriorate when models are applied across countries or auction environments, and Huber and Imhof (2023) reinforces the broader point that predictive structure is sensitive to representation and context. This cross-jurisdiction evidence is directly relevant for screening policy because it implies that foreign training data may be informative yet insufficient for off-the-shelf deployment in a target jurisdiction.

What remains largely unexplored is how this portability problem interacts with label scarcity. Existing bid-rigging studies generally train supervised models under the implicit assumption that a sufficiently rich labeled archive is available. Yet confirmed cartel cases are costly to establish and may remain limited even when authorities possess large administrative

procurement datasets. To our knowledge, no prior study has systematically characterized within-country learning curves under extreme label scarcity in bid-rigging detection, nor quantified how much local supervised performance can be recovered as the domestic labeled sample expands.

Our contribution is to connect these strands. We study bid-rigging detection in an environment where both constraints arise jointly: models may transfer imperfectly across jurisdictions, and domestic labels may be scarce. We therefore examine, within a unified empirical design, cross-jurisdiction transportability and within-country learning curves under absolute label scarcity.

3 Institutional Setting, Data Construction, and Domain Heterogeneity

3.1 Institutional Domains and Data Sources

The empirical analysis relies on the multi-jurisdiction procurement dataset assembled by García Rodríguez et al. (2022). The benchmark combines confirmed cartel cases and competitive tenders from several institutional environments and has already been used as a comparative benchmark for supervised collusion-detection methods.

The restricted sample used in this study comprises five institutional domains: Brazil, Japan, the United States, Switzerland, and Ticino. Although the Swiss subsamples share a common federal legal framework, they differ markedly in observed bidding patterns and cartel exposure, reflecting variation in local market structure and enforcement history. Italy is excluded because its average-bid auction format differs mechanically from the lowest-bid rules prevailing in the remaining domains, which would compromise comparability for the dispersion- and relative-positioning features that play a central role in the analysis.

The unit of observation for model estimation is the bidder–tender pair. This granularity allows us to retain all bids and to construct bidder-level predictors capturing both absolute bidding behaviour and relative positioning within the auction. At the same time, many of the screening variables are functions of the tender-level bid distribution, and the practical object of investigation for a competition authority is ultimately the tender rather than the individual bid. For that reason, the empirical analysis combines bid-level training with tender-level aggregation in the evaluation stage.

3.2 Label Construction and Sample Composition

The binary label indicating collusive participation is derived from cartel cases identified and sanctioned by competition authorities in the respective jurisdictions. Tenders associated with confirmed cartel episodes are labeled as collusive ($y = 1$), while remaining tenders are labeled as competitive ($y = 0$). This labeling strategy follows established practice in the empirical literature on bid-rigging detection and makes supervised classification feasible.

The relatively high positive rate observed in the restricted sample should not be interpreted as the prevalence of collusion in procurement markets. Rather, it is a feature of the benchmark design. As documented by García Rodríguez et al. (2022), the dataset was assembled by

combining confirmed cartel cases with competitive tenders in order to facilitate systematic comparative evaluation of detection methods across jurisdictions. Performance measures reported below should therefore be interpreted as conditional on this curated sample rather than as direct estimates of field performance under natural market prevalence.

The final restricted sample contains 40,960 bids across 9,446 tenders. Each tender includes on average 4.3 bids (median 3). In the bid-level dataset, the overall collusive share is 0.4964. This aggregate figure, however, masks substantial cross-domain heterogeneity in both sample size and class composition, reflecting differences in enforcement history, sectoral composition, and the structure of confirmed cartel cases.

3.3 Feature Construction

The explanatory variables consist of screening indicators derived from the distribution of bids within each auction. These include the submitted bid value, the number of bids received, dispersion measures such as the coefficient of variation and standardized price dispersion, relative bid differences such as the distance from the winning bid and percentage deviation, winner indicators, and distributional statistics including skewness, kurtosis, and Kolmogorov–Smirnov test statistics. Their construction follows established approaches in the collusion-screening literature (Imhof et al., 2018; Imhof, 2019).

These variables are economically motivated. Dispersion and relative-distance measures capture bid coordination and price clustering consistent with collusive equilibria. Participation variables reflect possible market-allocation or bid-rotation patterns. Distributional moments summarize asymmetries that may arise under coordinated bidding strategies. Each bid is therefore represented by a harmonized set of numeric screens designed to be comparable across domains, even though the institutional environments themselves differ.

3.4 Descriptive Evidence on Domain Heterogeneity

The five domains differ not only in legal and procurement environments, but also in observed sample composition. This is already visible in simple descriptive evidence from the restricted benchmark. At the bid level, collusive shares range from 0.1015 in Japan and 0.1773 in the United States to 0.8028 in Switzerland and 0.8156 in Ticino, with Brazil at 0.2097. A Pearson chi-squared test strongly rejects independence between domain and collusive status ($\chi^2 = 18377.69$, $p < 0.001$), confirming that domain composition is tightly associated with the target label.

Key auction characteristics also differ markedly across domains. In particular, the mean number of bids ranges from 2.30 in the United States to 13.22 in Japan, with intermediate values of 9.34 in Brazil, 6.11 in Switzerland, and 7.64 in Ticino. An analysis of variance rejects equality of means across domains by a wide margin ($F = 19873.21$, $p < 0.001$); the corresponding Kruskal–Wallis test leads to the same conclusion ($H = 28019.46$, $p < 0.001$). These differences are not trivial in magnitude: the associated effect size is large ($\eta^2 = 0.66$). This implies that variables often treated as generic auction screens may also encode institutional structure, particularly participation measures such as `Number_bids`. Consistent with this interpretation, exploratory domain-specific analysis indicates that the sample association between `Number_bids` and collusive status is not uniform across jurisdictions: it

is negative in Brazil and Japan, positive in the United States and Switzerland, and weakly negative in Ticino.

Table 1 summarizes this heterogeneity at the domain level. The operational evaluation unit in this work is the tender, and the tender-level collusive share also varies sharply across domains, from 0.1139 in Japan and 0.1297 in the United States to 0.7350 in Switzerland and 0.8214 in Ticino, with Brazil at 0.3267. Hence, the heterogeneity is not an artifact of bidder-level duplication within tenders; it is also visible at the level at which competition authorities would prioritize investigations.

These descriptive patterns are substantively important for screening. A model estimated in one domain may exploit regularities that are highly predictive within that environment but less stable outside it. The heterogeneity concerns not only the distribution of the screens themselves, but also their empirical association with collusive status. The concern is not merely technical: the observable manifestations of collusion may themselves depend on procurement rules, bidder pools, reserve-price practices, and cartel organization. For that reason, the empirical design developed in the next section does not rely on IID-style evaluation alone. Instead, it explicitly separates cross-domain transfer from within-domain learning under label scarcity.

Table 1: Descriptive heterogeneity across domains in the restricted benchmark

Domain	Bids	Tenders	Tender-level collusive share	Mean bids per tender
Brazil	682	101	0.3267	6.76
USA	6959	3754	0.1297	1.87
Switzerland	20873	4287	0.7350	4.88
Ticino	1307	224	0.8214	6.81
Japan	11139	1080	0.1139	12.51
Total	40960	9446	0.4211	4.34

Notes: The table reports descriptive statistics for the restricted five-domain benchmark used in this work. Collusive shares are computed at the tender level. Mean bids per tender is the domain-specific average number of bids in the tender-level collapsed data.

4 Experimental Design Under Label Scarcity

4.1 Empirical Strategy

The empirical design is built to answer two distinct but related questions. First, how much predictive performance is lost when a model trained outside a jurisdiction is applied to that jurisdiction? Second, conditional on imperfect external portability, how many domestic labels are required to recover effective jurisdiction-specific screening performance?

We address these questions with two complementary experiments. The first is a leave-one-domain-out (LODO) evaluation, which measures cross-jurisdiction transfer under institutional heterogeneity. The second estimates within-country learning curves by varying the absolute number of labeled tenders available for training. Throughout, the objective is not to

benchmark algorithms in the abstract, nor to claim that the same predictive structure is portable across settings, but to characterize the practical feasibility of jurisdiction-specific screening under realistic informational constraints.

For the within-country experiments, each jurisdiction is split 80/20 into a training pool and a held-out test set using group-aware splitting so that no tender appears in both sets. This prevents information leakage through multiple bids from the same procurement procedure and mirrors the operational scenario in which an authority deploys a model on new tenders drawn from its own procurement environment.

Within each jurisdiction, we vary the number of labeled tenders available for training over the grid

$$N \in \{5, 10, 20, 40, 80, 120\}. \tag{1}$$

For a given value of N , we randomly select N training tenders to be treated as labeled, stratifying at the tender level whenever feasible. All remaining training tenders are treated as unlabeled. The design is repeated across random seeds in order to characterize sampling variability. This formulation is more directly policy-relevant than a labeled-fraction design because it maps predictive performance into the number of domestic procurement procedures that would need to be labeled by an authority.

For each jurisdiction, we define the local oracle as the supervised XGBoost model trained on the full labeled training pool of that jurisdiction. All learning-curve results are interpreted relative to this benchmark. The question of interest is therefore not whether sparse-label models match an abstract optimum, but how much of the best attainable local supervised performance can be recovered with only a small number of labeled domestic tenders.

In addition to the nominal labeled-set size, we track the mean number of positive labeled tenders associated with each nominal N , which allows us to report a complementary policy-oriented view in terms of confirmed collusion cases rather than total labeled tenders. Primary visualizations are therefore presented against total labeled tenders in the main text and, in the appendix, against positive labeled tenders.

All labeled observations are used for training; no separate validation set is reserved. This reflects a realistic enforcement scenario in which scarce confirmed cases would not be set aside for tuning. Hyperparameters are selected *ex ante* and then held fixed across experiments to avoid implicit validation leakage. Feature preprocessing is estimated from the labeled subset available in each repetition and then applied to the remaining training data and the held-out test set. This mirrors the informational constraints faced by competition authorities and avoids using unlabeled observations when constructing the supervised training transformation.

Our primary evaluation metric is Average Precision (AP) on the held-out test set. AP is appropriate for this setting because the practical task is not to classify tenders at a single fixed threshold, but to rank them for potential investigation. It therefore summarizes screening quality over the full precision–recall trade-off rather than at an arbitrary operating point (Davis and Goadrich, 2006; Saito and Rehmsmeier, 2015). Because the benchmark is curated and class prevalences differ sharply across jurisdictions, raw AP comparisons are interpreted with caution in the cross-jurisdiction analysis; where relevant, we therefore complement them with prevalence-adjusted comparisons that net out the jurisdiction-specific baseline (Boyd et al., 2012).

4.2 Models

XGBoost (Chen and Guestrin, 2016) is used as the reference supervised model throughout this work. It is implemented as a gradient-boosted decision-tree classifier with 200 estimators, learning rate 0.05, maximum depth 4, subsampling rate 0.85, column subsampling 0.85, and L_2 regularization $\lambda = 1.0$. Class imbalance is addressed through `scale_pos_weight`, computed from the labeled subset available in each repetition. This model also defines the local oracle when trained on the full labeled training pool within a jurisdiction.

This choice is substantively appropriate for the present setting. Our data are medium-sized, tabular, and built from engineered screening variables that are likely to interact nonlinearly across procurement environments. Gradient-boosted trees are well suited to that regime because they can capture nonlinearities and higher-order interactions without requiring heavy functional-form specification, while remaining competitive on structured tabular problems relative to more elaborate alternatives (Chen and Guestrin, 2016; Grinsztajn et al., 2022). In addition, XGBoost accommodates class imbalance directly through weighting and includes regularization and subsampling devices that help control overfitting when the domestic labeled seed is small. These properties make XGBoost a credible reference supervised model for the present setting, rather than a deliberately weak comparator.

4.3 Leave-One-Domain-Out (LODO) Evaluation

To assess cross-jurisdiction transfer under genuine distribution shift, we conduct Leave-One-Domain-Out (LODO) evaluation. In each fold, one jurisdiction is designated as the target domain and excluded entirely from the transfer model’s training data. The transfer model is then trained on all remaining jurisdictions and evaluated on the held-out jurisdiction.

For each target jurisdiction, we construct a local comparison benchmark on the same country. Specifically, the target-country data are first split into an 80% local training subset and a 20% local test subset at the tender level. The local oracle is trained on the 80% local training subset using all available local labels, and both the local oracle and the transfer model are evaluated on the identical 20% target-country test split. This design ensures that the ratio between transfer performance and local-oracle performance is a like-for-like comparison on common test data. The LODO experiment therefore answers a practical portability question: to what extent can a screening model trained elsewhere be deployed off the shelf in a concrete target jurisdiction? Its purpose is not to establish whether the model captures a universal signature of collusion but to quantify how much locally attainable predictive performance survives transfer across institutional settings.

5 Results

5.1 Cross-Domain Transfer (LODO)

We begin with the transportability question. In the LODO experiment, an XGBoost model is trained on all jurisdictions except the target one and evaluated on a held-out 20% test split of that target jurisdiction. Crucially, the local oracle is evaluated on the *same* target-country

Table 2: Cross-jurisdiction transferability measured by the prevalence-adjusted signal ratio (ASR, cf. expr.2) and its standard error.

Country	LODO ASR	Std. Error
Brazil	0.517	0.064
Japan	0.048	0.005
Switzerland	0.021	0.015
Ticino	-0.189	0.082
USA	0.423	0.024

test set, after being trained on the remaining 80% of the target jurisdiction. This design makes the transfer-oracle comparison a like-for-like exercise on identical test data.

To make this comparison meaningful across jurisdictions with very different test prevalences, we report a prevalence-adjusted transferability measure rather than relying only on raw AP ratios. Specifically, for each jurisdiction we compute the adjusted signal ratio (ASR):

$$\text{ASR}_{\text{transfer}} = \frac{AP_{\text{transfer}} - \pi_{\text{test}}}{AP_{\text{oracle}} - \pi_{\text{test}}}, \quad (2)$$

where π_{test} is the positive-rate baseline in the held-out-country test split. This object measures the share of the local oracle’s *excess signal above baseline* that survives cross-jurisdiction transfer. Table 2 reports repeated-split LODO estimates and their associated standard errors.

The prevalence-adjusted view sharpens the main lesson of the transfer exercise. Foreign data are informative, but off-the-shelf deployment remains uneven across jurisdictions. Transferability is moderate in Brazil and the United States, very limited in Japan, close to zero in Switzerland, and negative in Ticino once the very high prevalence baseline is netted out. The policy implication is therefore not that foreign evidence is useless, but that its practical value depends on how much jurisdiction-specific predictive structure is lost in transfer. This makes local adaptation the central operational issue.

Before turning to local learning under label scarcity, it is useful to report the absolute level of the jurisdiction-specific local oracle that anchors the transfer comparison. Table 3 reports the mean Average Precision of the supervised XGBoost oracle in each jurisdiction, evaluated on the same held-out 20% target-country test split used in the LODO exercise, together with standard errors across repeated splits. These values provide the absolute benchmark against which both cross-jurisdiction transferability and within-country adjusted recovery should be interpreted.

5.2 The Within-Country Learning Curve Under Label Scarcity

Given the limited portability documented above, the relevant policy question is not only whether domestic labels improve jurisdiction-specific screening, but how many are needed to recover substantively meaningful local performance. To compare within-country learning directly with cross-jurisdiction transfer, we therefore express the local learning curves on

Table 3: Jurisdiction-specific local oracle performance in the LODO/within-country design. The table reports the mean Average Precision of the supervised XGBoost oracle trained on the full labeled local training pool of each jurisdiction and evaluated on the same held-out 20% test split used in the LODO exercise, together with standard errors across repeated splits.

Country	Oracle AP	SE
Brazil	0.833	0.024
Japan	0.705	0.014
Switzerland	0.937	0.002
Ticino	0.991	0.002
USA	0.425	0.010

the same prevalence-adjusted scale used in the LODO analysis. For each jurisdiction, the within-country adjusted recovery metric is

$$\text{ASR}_{\text{local}}(N) = \frac{AP_{\text{local}}(N) - \pi_{\text{test}}}{AP_{\text{oracle}} - \pi_{\text{test}}}, \quad (3)$$

where $AP_{\text{local}}(N)$ is the Average Precision obtained with N labeled domestic tenders, AP_{oracle} is the local oracle benchmark, and π_{test} is the positive-rate baseline in the corresponding test set. This object measures the share of the local oracle’s excess AP above baseline that is recovered with a scarce domestic labeled set.

Figure 1 compares these within-country adjusted recovery curves with the corresponding LODO transfer benchmark for each jurisdiction. The horizontal dashed line marks the repeated-split LODO estimate, while the local curve shows how quickly domestic labels recover jurisdiction-specific signal. Read in this way, the figure provides a direct answer to the paper’s central operational question: when does local adaptation overtake the predictive value of importing a model trained abroad?

To complement this prevalence-adjusted view, Figure 2 reports the corresponding supervised learning curves in raw Average Precision for each jurisdiction, together with the local oracle evaluated on the same held-out target-country test split. This absolute-scale representation makes explicit both the heterogeneity in attainable local performance and the fact that outperforming a weak transfer benchmark need not imply coming close to the best attainable local benchmark.

This comparison yields two distinct insights. First, in several jurisdictions, even small domestic labeled sets already outperform the signal obtainable from off-the-shelf transfer. This is especially clear in Switzerland and Ticino, where the local adjusted-recovery curves lie above the LODO benchmark from the smallest labeled-set sizes onward, and in Brazil, where the local curve rises above transfer very quickly. By contrast, the United States remains much more demanding: local learning improves only gradually and does not clearly dominate transfer until substantially larger labeled sets. Japan occupies an intermediate position: transferability is very weak, so local models surpass the transfer benchmark early, but the recovery of *strong* local performance remains much slower.

Second, and importantly, this new comparison should be read primarily as evidence that

Local adjusted recovery versus LODO transferability

Figure 1: Within-country prevalence-adjusted recovery curves for supervised XGBoost, together with the corresponding LODO transfer benchmark for each jurisdiction. The vertical axis reports the share of the local oracle’s excess AP above the prevalence baseline recovered at each labeled-set size (cf. expr.3). The horizontal dashed line marks the repeated-split LODO estimate for the same jurisdiction (cf. Table 2); shaded bands denote standard errors.

Within-country supervised learning curves and local oracle

Figure 2: Within-country supervised learning curves in raw Average Precision, together with the jurisdiction-specific local oracle. Each panel reports the mean Average Precision of supervised XGBoost at each labeled-set size. The horizontal dashed line marks the mean local oracle performance obtained when training supervised XGBoost on the full labeled local training pool; shaded bands denote standard errors across repeated splits.

Table 4: Prevalence-adjusted label efficiency in the within-country experiment. For each country, the table reports the cross-jurisdiction transfer benchmark (2nd column, cf. Table 2), the minimum labeled-set size needed to reach 80% of the local oracle under the adjusted criterion (3rd column), the corresponding minimum average number of positive labeled tenders (4th column), and the maximum adjusted oracle-recovery level attained within the main experimental grid (5th column, cf. expr.1. All adjusted signal measures are expressed in percentage points of oracle recovery.

Country	LODO %	Min N for 80%	Min \bar{N}_+	Max %
Brazil	51.7	10	3	92.1
Japan	4.8	> 120	> 14	77.5
Switzerland	2.1	> 120	> 88	61.7
Ticino	-18.9	20	16	101.2
USA	42.3	> 120	> 15	43.7

imported models are easy to outperform locally in several jurisdictions, *not* as evidence that five labeled tenders are generally sufficient to build a strong domestic screening model. In some jurisdictions the LODO benchmark is itself very weak once prevalence is taken into account, so surpassing it may require only modest local adaptation. For that reason, the main measure of label efficiency remains recovery of the local oracle rather than the point at which transfer is overtaken.

Table 4 restores that oracle-based perspective by reporting the minimum labeled-set size required to reach 80% of local oracle performance under the prevalence-adjusted criterion, together with the corresponding mean number of positive labeled tenders and the maximum adjusted recovery attained within the main experimental grid. For jurisdictions that do not reach the threshold, the table reports the threshold as exceeding the maximum value observed in the main grid.

Brazil reaches the adjusted 80% threshold with 10 labeled tenders despite a non-trivial transfer benchmark, whereas Ticino reaches it with 20 labeled tenders after starting from a negative transfer baseline. By contrast, Japan, Switzerland, and the United States do not reach the adjusted 80% threshold within the restricted grid, although for very different reasons: Japan starts from weak transfer but approaches the oracle more closely than Switzerland, while the United States remains the most difficult local learning environment overall.

Taken together, the figure and the threshold table clarify the role of scarce domestic labels. In some jurisdictions, a modest local seed is sufficient to outperform cross-jurisdiction transfer. But the stronger requirement—recovering a large share of the best attainable local performance—remains heterogeneous across institutional settings. This is why this study’s central constraint is not label scarcity in isolation, but the interaction between scarce domestic labels and imperfect transportability across jurisdictions.

6 Discussion and Conclusions

This work studies a deployment problem that is central to data-driven cartel screening in public procurement. Competition authorities may possess large administrative procurement datasets, yet the stock of confirmed cartel cases available for model development can remain limited. At the same time, predictive patterns learned in one jurisdiction may not transfer reliably to another. Our empirical design is built to study these two constraints jointly rather than in isolation: cross-jurisdiction transferability through LODO evaluation and within-country learning under scarce labels through absolute- N learning curves benchmarked against a local oracle.

The first main conclusion concerns transportability. Once transfer performance is interpreted on a prevalence-adjusted basis, the evidence in our benchmark points to limited and highly heterogeneous portability across jurisdictions. This does not overturn earlier work that had already documented imperfect transferability; rather, it shows that the loss of portability can appear especially marked when benchmarked against a jurisdiction-specific local oracle on an adjusted scale. Foreign data are informative, but models trained elsewhere do not generally preserve a large share of the jurisdiction-specific predictive signal attainable with local supervision. This strengthens the interpretation that procurement rules, bidder composition, reserve-price practices, market organization, and cartel structure generate predictive regularities that are at least partly domain-dependent rather than universally portable. In practical terms, the results caution against off-the-shelf deployment of imported screening models without local validation.

The second main conclusion concerns local label efficiency. Within a jurisdiction, supervised gradient boosting can recover a substantial share of the attainable local benchmark with a relatively modest domestic labeled seed, but the speed of recovery differs sharply across countries. In some jurisdictions, local learning curves rise quickly and overtake the cross-jurisdiction transfer benchmark with relatively few domestic labels. In others, recovery is much slower and remains well below the oracle over much of the experimental grid. This distinction is important. Surpassing imported transfer should be interpreted primarily as evidence that foreign models are relatively easy to outperform locally in some settings, not as evidence that very small domestic labeled sets are generally sufficient to build a strong screening tool. For that reason, the work treats recovery of the local oracle as the primary benchmark for label efficiency and uses the transfer comparison as a complementary operational benchmark rather than as a sufficient criterion of local readiness.

A related implication is methodological. In a curated benchmark such as ours, Average Precision is mechanically affected by the positive-rate baseline of the test set. Raw AP comparisons can therefore overstate cross-jurisdiction transportability when prevalences differ sharply across domains. The prevalence-adjusted comparisons sharpen the interpretation of both transfer and local recovery by focusing on excess predictive signal above the jurisdiction-specific baseline. This does not imply that raw AP is uninformative, but it does imply that policy conclusions about portability should not be based on raw AP alone. Taken together, the results suggest a clear hierarchy of constraints in this benchmark. The more persistent obstacle is not label scarcity in the abstract, but the interaction between scarce domestic labels and imperfect cross-jurisdiction transportability. Where institutional heterogeneity is substantial, even a modest local archive can be more informative than foreign training data

used without adaptation. Conversely, where transportability is somewhat stronger, imported models may still provide useful early screening value, but local labels remain important if the goal is to recover a large share of the best attainable jurisdiction-specific performance.

These findings have direct policy implications. Authorities should not view the choice as one between relying entirely on imported models and waiting until a very large domestic case archive has been assembled. A more pragmatic strategy is suggested by the evidence: use foreign data cautiously as auxiliary information, validate performance locally, and invest in building a small but credible domestic labeled seed that can support jurisdiction-specific adaptation. In some jurisdictions, the amount of domestic labeling effort required to obtain non-trivial screening value can be modest, although this remains strongly context-dependent. Because the analysis also tracks the mean number of positive labeled tenders associated with each nominal N , the appendix re-expresses the same learning process on the axis of confirmed collusion cases, which may be the more natural policy object when enforcement capacity is the binding resource.

The study also has limitations. First, the benchmark is curated from confirmed cartel cases and competitive tenders, so the reported metrics should be interpreted conditionally on this design rather than as direct estimates of screening performance at natural market prevalence. Second, the analysis covers five institutional domains and a specific family of screen-based tabular representations, so the results speak to an important but still bounded set of procurement environments. Accordingly, the severity of the transportability losses documented here should be interpreted as conditional on this curated five-domain benchmark, the particular mix of institutional environments it contains, and the prevalence-adjusted evaluation framework adopted in the study. Third, the current empirical design remains centered on predictive performance rather than downstream institutional objectives such as investigation cost, legal burden of proof, or welfare-weighted ranking losses.

These limitations point naturally to future research. A first priority is to study transfer methods that are explicitly designed for institutional heterogeneity. A second is to integrate labeling cost more directly into the analysis, for example through active-learning or case-selection strategies that target the most informative tenders for investigation and adjudication. A third is to expand the evidence base to additional procurement regimes, sectors, and auction formats, including settings in which labels are weaker, delayed, or only partially verified. A fourth is to investigate whether alternative representations of procurement data—including relational or network-based structures—alter the relative performance of local supervised and transfer-oriented approaches under scarce labels. The broader conclusion is therefore cautious but constructive. Our results suggest that data-driven screening for bid rigging can remain feasible under informational constraints in curated benchmark settings such as ours, but its success depends less on importing a universally valid model than on adapting prediction to the institutional environment in which it will be used. Limited domestic labels do not preclude useful deployment. What they point to is the need for a jurisdiction-specific strategy that treats foreign evidence as a complement, not a substitute, for local learning.

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A Pooled Learning in a Synthetic Jurisdiction

As a secondary exercise, we also estimate learning curves on the pooled multi-country sample. We interpret this pooled setting as a *synthetic jurisdiction* that combines heterogeneous procurement environments. It is not meant to represent a deployable model for any specific country. Rather, it provides auxiliary evidence on how quickly predictive signal can be recovered in a mixed environment that contains some characteristics of many jurisdictions and exactly matches none of them.

This distinction matters for interpretation. The pooled benchmark can be informative about label efficiency under heterogeneity, but it is not a substitute for the transportability question studied in the main text. For that question, the relevant object is the prevalence-adjusted LODO comparison against a concrete target jurisdiction. The pooled exercise should therefore be read as a descriptive benchmark for learning in a mixed environment, not as evidence that a model trained on pooled international data can be deployed off the shelf in a specific country.

Figure 3 compares the pooled XGBoost learning curve with the jurisdiction-specific supervised curves. The pooled benchmark can exceed weak local learners at very small labeled-set sizes, most clearly in Japan and the United States, where local learning is initially slow. By contrast, it remains well below the jurisdiction-specific curves in Switzerland and Ticino, and below Brazil once a modest local seed is available. The substantive lesson is therefore limited but useful: pooling heterogeneous jurisdictions can generate a learner with some early predictive value, but that value should not be confused with jurisdiction-specific adaptation.

The same comparison is also reported on the confirmed-cases axis in Appendix B. That representation is useful when the relevant policy object is not the total number of labeled tenders but the number of confirmed collusion cases required to achieve a given level of predictive performance.

Overall, the pooled benchmark plays a limited but clarifying role in the work. It shows that some predictive signal can be recovered in a mixed international environment, but it also reinforces the main conclusion of the paper: for deployment in a concrete jurisdiction, the relevant comparison is not pooled performance in the abstract, but the balance between prevalence-adjusted transferability and jurisdiction-specific local learning.

Figure 3: Within-country supervised XGBoost learning curves compared with the pooled multi-source benchmark. The pooled curve is interpreted as a synthetic-jurisdiction reference rather than as a deployable country-specific model.

B Additional Within-Country Outputs

This appendix reports additional within-country representations that complement, but do not replace, the main-text results. Their purpose is to re-express the same learning process on a more policy-oriented axis when the binding institutional resource is interpreted as confirmed collusion cases rather than labeled tenders more generally.

Specifically, it reports three additional views on the confirmed-cases axis: the supervised learning curves, the corresponding oracle-recovery curves, and the pooled synthetic-jurisdiction benchmark.

Figure 4 shows the within-country learning curves by confirmed cases. The qualitative ranking of jurisdictions remains broadly consistent with the main text. Switzerland and Ticino still exhibit very strong local learning from small domestic seeds, Brazil improves rapidly once a few positive cases are available, Japan requires substantially more confirmed cases before approaching its local oracle, and the United States remains the most difficult environment in the sample.

Figure 5 reports the corresponding oracle-recovery curves. This figure is the confirmed-cases analogue of the oracle-based label-efficiency analysis in the main text. It is especially useful for policy interpretation because it makes explicit how many positive cases, on average, are associated with each stage of local performance recovery. In several jurisdictions, the required number remains modest, but the gap across countries is substantial.

Finally, Figure 6 reports the pooled synthetic-jurisdiction benchmark from Appendix A on the confirmed-cases axis. As in the main pooled comparison, the pooled benchmark may exceed weak local learners at very small seeds, but it should not be interpreted as evidence of deployable cross-jurisdiction transportability.

Taken together, these appendix figures serve a supporting role. They do not change the main conclusions of the paper, but they provide a useful alternative representation when confirmed cases are the most natural unit for thinking about domestic labeling effort.

Within-country supervised learning curves and local oracle as a function of positive labeled tenders (confirmed cases)

Figure 4: Within-country learning curves as a function of the average number of positive labeled tenders (confirmed collusion cases).

Figure 5: Percentage of oracle performance recovered by supervised XGBoost as a function of the average number of positive labeled tenders.

Figure 6: Jurisdiction-specific supervised learning curves and the pooled synthetic-jurisdiction benchmark, plotted against the average number of positive labeled tenders.

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